

Lessons learned from COVID 19

Importance of timely and free access to scientific data, publications, information

Importance of science-policy-society dialogue

Importance of scientific collaborations and sharing of information at all levels

Importance of Open Science

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Opening access to knowledge

Source: Dimensions

Why Open Science? Open access and much more...

UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science

Need for an international policy and action framework

Need for a common definition of open science, shared set of values and principles

In 2019, at the UNESCO 40th General Conference, 193 Members States tasked UNESCO with the development of an international standard-setting instrument on Open Science in the form of a UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science.

UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science

Text of the Recommendation developed through a broad consultative, inclusive, transparent multistakeholder two-year process

**Adopted by 193 countries at the UNESCO
General Conference on 23 November 2021**

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Highlights of the Recommendation

- ❖ It is the first **international normative instrument** on Open Science;
- ❖ it contains the first **internationally agreed definition** of Open Science;
- ❖ it spells out the consensus **core values and guiding principles** of Open Science;
- ❖ it addresses **multiple actors and stakeholders** of Open Science;
- ❖ It recommends **actions on different levels** to operationalize the principles of Open Science;
- ❖ it proposes **innovative approaches for Open Science at different stages** of the scientific cycle;
- ❖ it calls for development of a **comprehensive Open Science monitoring framework**.

Definition of Open Science

Open Science:

- ❖ makes *multilingual* scientific knowledge openly available, accessible and reusable for everyone,
- ❖ increases scientific collaborations and sharing of information for the benefits of science and society,
- ❖ opens the processes of scientific knowledge creation, evaluation and communication to societal actors beyond the traditional scientific community.

As open as possible and as closed as necessary

AS OPEN AS POSSIBLE

Access to scientific knowledge should be as open as possible, but sometimes access may need to be restricted, for example to protect human rights, confidentiality, intellectual property rights, personal information, threatened or endangered species, and sacred and secret indigenous knowledge. Open science encourages scientists to develop tools and methods for managing data so that as much data as possible can be shared, as appropriate.

Open Science: Values and Principles

Key Objectives – Key Areas of Action

Member States are encouraged to prioritise seven areas in their implementation of the *Recommendation*:

1. Promoting a common understanding of OS and its associated benefits and challenges, as well as the diverse paths to OS
2. Developing an enabling policy environment for OS
3. Investing in infrastructure and services which contribute to OS
4. Investing in training, education, digital literacy and capacity-building, to enable researchers and other stakeholders to participate in OS
5. Fostering a culture of OS and aligning incentives for OS
6. Promoting innovative approaches to OS at different stages of the scientific process
7. Promoting international and multistakeholder cooperation in the context of OS with a view to reducing digital, technological and knowledge gaps.

At the international level...

- ❖ **Raising awareness**
- ❖ Developing a series of **supporting tools** - technical briefs, fact sheets and guidelines
- ❖ Collecting/mapping existing **open science policies and strategies**
- ❖ Collecting and sharing **best practices**
- ❖ Analyzing open science **financing mechanisms and incentives**
- ❖ Promoting open science **infrastructures**
- ❖ **Building capacity**
- ❖ Developing an **open science monitoring framework**

Key challenges and high impact areas for the implementation of the UNESCO OSR

Change in the conventional scientific culture

Human and institutional capacity

Adequate infrastructures, including reliable internet connectivity

Alignment of incentives and revision of criteria for evaluation of scientific excellence and scientific careers

Addressing the unintended negative consequences of open science practices

How Open Science?

Based on Centre for
Open Science's strategy
for cultural change

GUIDES

- **Building capacity** for open science
- **Developing policies for open science**
- **Funding** open science
- Bolstering open science **infrastructures** for all
- Engaging society

CHECKLISTS

- Checklist for **universities** on implementing the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science
- Checklist for **open access publishers** on implementing the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science

FACTSHEETS

- Understanding open science
- Identifying predatory academic journals and conferences

OPEN INDEXES OF OPEN SCIENCE RESOURCES

- UNESCO Open Science **Capacity Building index**
- UNESCO Index of Open Science **Knowledge Sharing Platforms**
- UNESCO Global Observatory of Science, Technology and Innovation **Policy Instruments (GO-SPIN)**

<https://www.unesco.org/en/open-science/toolkit>

PROMOTING OPEN SCIENCE AS A KEY FRAMEWORK FOR TRANSFORMATIVE INTERNATIONAL EQUITABLE SCIENTIFIC COOPERATION

Upcoming UNESCO Open
Science Outlook

Join the Global Open Science Movement

Join the UNESCO Open Science Partnership!

Contribute to global open science calls !

Engage in the global discussions!

Be in touch!

UNESCO Open science website:

<https://on.unesco.org/openscience>

Contact: openscience@unesco.org

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Thank you

Obrigado

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and Cultural Organization